

OECS Academic Recovery Programme

Implementation Planning: Implementation Planning Tool

Open Development & Education

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Commissioned by

The Organization of the Eastern Caribbean States

You context - fact sheet		
Filling in this fact sheet helps you establish the situation in your territory and share this among the team.		Hint
Contact information		
Your territory		Enter the name of your territory, e.g. Grenada.
Lead person implementing		Enter name / email / phone
Other team members (add rows as needed)		Enter name / email / phone
Other team members (add rows as needed)		Enter name / email / phone
School status		
How many school closures have you had?	Please use the 'school closures sheet' to record past closures and projected closures.	Enter number of school closures
On average, how long are the school closure for ?		Enter number of weeks/months
On average, how many more school closures are you expecting?		Enter number of projected school closures
Do you have an emergency plan for school closure?		Enter details of an emergency plan/ date which you plan to have one. Also, provide brief details of how education will continue during a crisis such as a pandemic or natural hazard.
Availability of technology		
How many students have access to devices at home?		Enter number/percentage of students who have access to laptops, tablets, phones etc at home. You can make notes if you do not know the exact numbers.
On average, how many homes have more than 1 device?		Enter number of homes where there is one device?
Internet Connectivity		
How many students have internet at home?		Enter number/percentage of students with internet at home. You can make notes if you do not know the exact numbers.
On average, how many students have stable internet connectivity at home?		Enter number/percentage of students who have stable internet connectivity at home. You can make notes if you do not know the exact numbers.

You context - fact sheet		
Filling in this fact sheet helps you establish the situation in your territory and share this among the team.		Hint
On average, how many students have poor internet connectivity at home?		Enter the average number/percentage of students with poor internet connectivity. You can make notes if you do not know the exact numbers.
Which geographic locations have strong internet connectivity?		Enter the rural or urban locations where there is strong connectivity.
Describe the status of internet connectivity at your school		Explain whether all classes have internet access and if the connectivity is stable or not.
Current status of teacher support (Component 1)		
Describe any measures that provide psycho-socio support to teachers?		Enter N/A if none available.
Describe any teacher professional development activities that have been undertaken specifically for academic recovery?		Enter N/A if none available.
Do you have a national mailing list of teachers?		Enter N/A if none is available
Is there a local school and or district whatsapp group to support teachers?		State whether there is a social media platform for teachers to support each other. If you have none explain whether or not there are plans to have one.
Describe the platform that teachers use for video conferencing, online lesson delivery ect.		Specify the platforms that teachers use to deliver lessons online, for conferencing or TPD. E.g. Zoom, Google Meet and so on.
Current status of diagnostic tools (Component 2)		
Describe any diagnostic tests undertaken this far.		Describe the number of diagnostic tests taken so far. The types of diagnostic tests taken so far.
What changes, for example changes in teaching activities, are undertaken from the results of diagnostic tests?		Describe whether teaching activities have been undertaken in response to the results of the diagnostic tests. If not, describe the plans to do so.
Are further diagnostic tests scheduled during the school year?		Enter N/A if none is available

You context - fact sheet		
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Is there a plan to communicate results with all parents during lockdown?		Describe plans that are in place to communicate diagnostic tests results to parents during lockdown. Include ways to get in touch with parents who are normally unreachable
Current status of SPED (Component 3)		
Describe any efforts to cater for SPED students during Covid19		Describe all measures taken to meet the learning needs of SPED students in blended learning
Has TPD been organized to support SPED and classroom teachers?		Describe any specific SPED TPD organized for the SPED team including classroom teachers.
Has a resource inventory been carried out to ascertain SPED needs?		Describe any audits that have been undertaken to ascertain SPED needs
Are appropriate accommodations made for SPED students during diagnostic testing?		Describe the nature of the accommodations put in place to cater for SPED students during diagnostic testing in the context of Covid 10 considerations.
Current status of resources (Component 4)		
Describe any OER resources that teachers have access to.		Enter N/A if none available.
Are sufficient resources in place to cater for students who are in the ARP?		Describe the current status of resources in place to cater for students participating in the ARP
Is there a detailed plan to acquire necessary resources both OER and others to facilitate the execution of the ARP?		Enter N/A if none available.
Current status of parental engagement (Component 5)		
Do you have contact details for parents? Do schools have those? Do you have a mailing list of all parents?		Describe the information that you do have. Enter N/A if none available.

You context - fact sheet		
Filling in this fact sheet helps you establish the situation in your territory and share this among the team.		Hint
On average, how many parents are fully engaged during the execution of the ARP?		Enter the average number of fully participating parents. Describe this as best as you can. As you speak with teachers, obtain further details.
Describe any efforts to support parents in helping their children at home.		Provide brief details of training and other efforts to equip parents to support their children at home.
Describe alternative plans to engage parents who are not supportive		Provide an outline of alternative plans to engage parents who are hard to reach and or not supportive.
Current status of community engagement (Component 6)		
Have you conducted an audit of community groups that you currently work with?		Provide details of audit results.
Have you identified new potential community groups that can support the ARP?		List with contact details of new potential partners
Describe exact contribution of community group		Provide details of how you want the community groups to support the ARP.
Describe any meetings which have been organized to meet old and new community groups.		Provide brief details of meeting dates and outcomes.
Are measures in place to safeguard students during their engagement with community groups?		Describe procedures in place to ensure that community groups are cleared to work with children. That is, they do not pose a threat to children in any way.
Is there an inventory of skills and resources capacity for each community group?		Identify skill set for community and accompanying training needs.
Current status of partnership (Component 7)		
Is there a database with potential new partners and old ones?		Enter N/A if none available.

You context - fact sheet

Filling in this fact sheet helps you establish the situation in your territory and share this among the team.

Hint

Have meetings be held or scheduled to determine nature of support needed by partners to support the ARP? Will meetings seek to foster shared goals, vision and values?

Provide brief descriptions of number of meetings and outcomes

Your Gantt chart									Months (funded)					Months (supported with existing resources)				
Instructions: Copy selected items from Components 1-7 to generate an overview. You will need to take some time to review the sheets 'Component 1' to 'Component 7' at this stage.																		
Component	Responsible	No.	Activity	Description	Also see	Human resource	Other resources	Cost needed (from OECS / GPE grant)	May 2021	Jun 2021	Jul 2021	Aug 2021	Sep 2021	Oct 2021	Nov 2021	Dec 2021	Jan 2022	Feb 2022

Results-based monitoring and evaluation framework for the ARP							
Instructions: Copy selected items from Components 1-7 and the RBMF sheet to generate an overview							
Component	Responsible	Activities	Outputs	Performance indicators	Means of verification	Outcome	Assumptions
Component 1. Supporting teachers and instructors	Ministry of Education / EDMU School administrators and principals Teachers	1.1.1. Planning psychosocial and social support for teaching staff and instructors 1.1.2. Establish support network for teachers 1.1.3. TPD - Session plans 1.1.4. Implementing psychosocial / social support for teaching staff and instructors 1.2.1. TPD - Facilitator selection 1.2.2. TPD - Planning 1.2.3. TPD - Material production and distribution 1.2.4. TPD - Evaluation 1.3.1. TPD - Co-facilitation and delivery					
Component 2. Diagnostic tools and assessment	Ministry of Education / EDMU Teachers	2.1.1.. Monitoring of diagnostic test data 2.1.2.. Record progress in diagnostic testing. 2.2.1. Planning and administering diagnostic tests 2.2.2. Incorporate test results into lesson plans and pre- and reteaching activities 2.2.3. Building diagnostic tests for SPED 2.2.4. Delivery of TPD on diagnostic tests					
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	Ministry of Education / EDMU Ministry of Health School administrators and principals SPED / classroom teachers	3.1.1. Evaluate the current digital divide with regard to SPED 3.1.2. Ensure robust M&E systems and identification processes 3.1.3. Clearly define the roles of stakeholders 3.1.4. Close technology and resource gaps 3.1.5. Provide resources to teachers and instructors 3.1.6. Build partnerships with parents / caregivers 3.1.7. Work towards increased staffing 3.1.8. Content sourcing for SPED 3.1.9. Recruit and train more SPED teachers and instructors 3.2.1. Collaborate with MoE on diagnosis 3.2.2. Collaborate with MoE on strategy 3.2.3. Contribute to designing of TPD 3.2.4. Awareness campaign rollout 3.3.1. Engage with SPED identification processes 3.3.2. Partnerships with SPED specialists and organisations 3.3.3. Keep records of SPED students 3.4.1. SPED student evaluation / planning 3.4.2. Engaging parents of SPED students 3.4.3. Supporting SPED students 3.4.4. Participate in TPD sessions 3.4.5. Keep records, use support plans and referrals 3.4.6. Source for content online 3.4.7. Administer diagnostic tests and deliver feedback					
Component 4. Resource library: Open Educational Resources	Ministry of Education / EDMU School administrators and principals Teachers	4.1.1. Content inventory 4.1.2. Content sourcing 4.1.3. Review content 4.1.4. Content curation and alignment 4.1.5. Material development 4.2.1. Collate required inventory of resources 4.2.2. Resource allocation and pooling 4.2.3. Test OERs and ensure teacher competency 4.3.1. Resource inventory and allocation 4.3.2. Resource storage and access management 4.3.3. Ensure safeguarding of students and student information					
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	Ministry of Education / EDMU School administrators and principals Teachers	5.1.1. Conduct parental needs assessment 5.1.2. Review existing content created for parents 5.1.3. Update exiting content for parents and develop new content as needed 5.1.4. Roll out content 5.1.5. Radio campaign 5.1.6. Redefine counsellor roles 5.1.7. Develop plan for increasing the number of counsellors 5.2.1. Support parental needs assessment 5.2.2. Make information available to the designated authorities 5.2.3. Inform parents about the availability of new content 5.2.4. Strengthen links with PTA 5.2.5. Developing engagement protocols for parents 5.3.1. Disseminate and collect questionnaires 5.3.2. Submit questionnaire responses 5.3.3. Support dissemination of resources to parents 5.3.4. Identify, support, and refer					

Results-based monitoring and evaluation framework for the ARP							
Instructions: Copy selected items from Components 1-7 and the RBMF sheet to generate an overview							
Component	Responsible	Activities	Outputs	Performance indicators	Means of verification	Outcome	Assumptions
Component 6. Community engagement	Ministry of Education / EDMU School administrators and principals Teachers	6.1.1. Identify organisations and individuals 6.1.2. Define shared goals / objectives 6.1.3. Establish a role for appropriate individuals and organisations 6.2.1. Involve teachers and staff 6.2.2. Set up a community engagement team 6.2.3. Approach community group leaders 6.2.4. Engage partners 6.2.5. Promote counselling and referrals as needed 6.2.6. Evaluate training needs 6.2.7. Implement training and processes 6.3.1. Join / support community engagement team					
Component 7. Partnerships	Ministry of Education / EDMU / EDMU School Administrators and Principals School administrators and principals Teachers	7.1.1. Desk-based research 7.1.2. Partnership modelling 7.1.3. Partnership evaluation 7.1.4. Establish new partnerships 7.1.6. Record keeping 7.2.1. Inform teachers about partnerships 7.2.2. Review existing partnerships 7.2.3. Set up partnerships working group 7.2.4. Identify potential partners 7.2.5. Check for aligned goals and values 7.2.6. Establish new partnerships 7.2.7. Determining the nature of partnerships 7.3.1. Participate in ARP staff meetings 7.3.2. Join or support ARP partnerships taskforce					

Record of school closures			
Instructions: Use this sheet to record school closures.			
Month	Primary Schools	Secondary Schools	Notes
2021-01-04			
2021-01-11			
2021-01-18			
2021-01-25			
2021-02-01			
2021-02-08			
2021-02-15			
2021-02-22			
2021-03-01			
2021-03-08			
2021-03-15			
2021-03-22			
2021-03-29			
2021-04-05			
2021-04-12			
2021-04-19			
2021-04-26			
2021-05-03			
2021-05-10			
2021-05-17			
2021-05-24			
2021-05-31			
2021-06-07			
2021-06-14			
2021-06-21			
2021-06-28			

Record of school closures			
Instructions: Use this sheet to record school closures.			
Month	Primary Schools	Secondary Schools	Notes
2021-07-05			
2021-07-12			
2021-07-19			
2021-07-26			
2021-08-02			
2021-08-09			
2021-08-16			
2021-08-23			
2021-08-30			
2021-09-06			
2021-09-13			
2021-09-20			
2021-09-27			
2021-10-04			
2021-10-11			
2021-10-18			
2021-10-25			
2021-11-01			
2021-11-08			
2021-11-15			
2021-11-22			
2021-11-29			
2021-12-06			
2021-12-13			
2021-12-20			
2021-12-27			

Record of school closures			
Instructions: Use this sheet to record school closures.			
Month	Primary Schools	Secondary Schools	Notes
2022-01-03			
2022-01-10			
2022-01-17			
2022-01-24			
2022-01-31			
2022-02-07			
2022-02-14			
2022-02-21			
2022-02-28			
2022-03-07			
2022-03-14			
2022-03-21			
2022-03-28			
2022-04-04			
2022-04-11			
2022-04-18			
2022-04-25			
2022-05-02			
2022-05-09			
2022-05-16			
2022-05-23			
2022-05-30			
2022-06-06			
2022-06-13			
2022-06-20			
2022-06-27			

Record of school closures			
Instructions: Use this sheet to record school closures.			
Month	Primary Schools	Secondary Schools	Notes
2022-07-04			
2022-07-11			
2022-07-18			
2022-07-25			
2022-08-01			
2022-08-08			
2022-08-15			
2022-08-22			
2022-08-29			
2022-09-05			
2022-09-12			
2022-09-19			
2022-09-26			
2022-10-03			
2022-10-10			
2022-10-17			
2022-10-24			
2022-10-31			
2022-11-07			
2022-11-14			
2022-11-21			
2022-11-28			
2022-12-05			
2022-12-12			
2022-12-19			
2022-12-26			

Record of school closures			
Instructions: Use this sheet to record school closures.			
Month	Primary Schools	Secondary Schools	Notes
2023-01-02			

Component 1. Supporting teachers and instructors								Months (Funded)					Months (supported with existing resources)					
Component	Responsible	No.	Activity	Description	Also see	Human resource	Other resources	Cost needed (from OECS / GPE grant)	May 2021	Jun 2021	Jul 2021	Aug 2021	Sep 2021	Oct 2021	Nov 2021	Dec 2021	Jan 2022	Feb 2022
* Ministry of Education / EDMU																		
Component 1. Supporting teachers and instructors	Ministry of Education / EDMU	1.1.1	Planning psychosocial and social support for teaching staff and instructors	Determine the nature of the support that will be provided, establish frequency and plan how it will be monitored.		EDMU-ARP team	N/A	N/A	█									
Component 1. Supporting teachers and instructors	Ministry of Education / EDMU	1.1.2	Establish support network for teachers	Establish a network for teachers to support each other, promote sharing good practice, emotional support for teachers and problem solving. For example, such a network could consist of a set of WhatsApp groups, enabling teachers to reach out to each other.		Administrator to manage group sharing platform	N/A	N/A	█									
Component 1. Supporting teachers and instructors	Ministry of Education / EDMU	1.1.3	TPD - Session plans	The session plans available in this OECS ARP need to be tailored to suit the local context, for remote or face-to-face delivery. Develop at least 20 sessions for utilisation between May 2021 and February 2022. Session plans need to include materials on diagnostic testing and SPED, as well as on how to utilise new teaching resources, for both face-to-face teaching as well as remote learning. Key pedagogical techniques such as pair tutoring, talk, and play should be included.	2; 3; 4	Group of EDMU staff and teachers to contextualise the existing sample sessions and to develop further sessions.	Printed materials for sessions	N/A	█									
Component 1. Supporting teachers and instructors	Ministry of Education / EDMU	1.1.4	Implementing psychosocial / social support for teaching staff and instructors	Provision of counselling sessions or a counselling hotline to enable teachers deal better with the crisis.		Counsellors	Office, devices, connectivity, transport	(requires longer-term investments)						█	█	█	█	
* School administrators and principals																		
Component 1. Supporting teachers and instructors	School administrators and principals	1.2.1	TPD - Facilitator selection	Two peer-facilitators need to be selected in each school. These individuals should be enthusiastic and dedicated. They will implement the rollout of these school-based TPD. Each school should ensure that their pair of facilitators is paired with another pair from a different school. School management needs to oversee the selection and pairing process.	7	Two peer-facilitators per school (existing teachers, take up the role voluntarily). District or national coordinators.	Transportation (small stipend towards gas / bus)	XCD \$20 per trip	█									
Component 1. Supporting teachers and instructors	School administrators and principals	1.2.2	TPD - Planning	Each district should make decisions about when and how the sessions will take place (for example, after the school day, or during part of an abbreviated school day) Sessions should be either weekly or fortnightly. We recommend starting with weekly sessions, with the option for moving to fortnightly sessions later on. Principals should report the selected session dates to the relevant district or national coordinators. Develop contingency plans e.g. for technical issues / equipment failure (such as distributing materials via phone or hard copy in advance, using mobile networks instead of wifi etc.)		District coordinator / principals	Technician / some printed copies of material	XCD \$5 per copy	█	█								
Component 1. Supporting teachers and instructors	School administrators and principals	1.2.3	TPD - Material production and distribution	Decisions regarding how the ARP materials will be supplied should be discussed. Districts should decide whether handbooks will be printed or soft copies will be made available to teachers and facilitators. Also, each district should ensure that schools have the necessary equipment that facilitators should use to deliver the content. A contingency plan should be in place for equipment failure.		Existing staff to coordinate materials distribution.	Printed TPD manuals.	Costs for local printing. XCD \$5 / teacher.	█	█								
Component 1. Supporting teachers and instructors	School administrators and principals	1.2.4	TPD - Evaluation	Plan monitoring and evaluation of teacher performance after TPD. This should include self-evaluation as well as a summative evaluation at school level. Set up a web-based form, through which facilitators and teachers can report participation in - and outcomes of - the sessions. EDMU to analyse and review data. EDMU to feed results of analysis back to schools.		Facilitators and teachers. EDMU Consultant to EDMU may be needed to support evaluation.	Some printed copies of all material	Consultant				█	█	█	█			
* Teachers																		

Component 1. Supporting teachers and instructors									Months (Funded)					Months (supported with existing resources)				
Component	Responsible	No.	Activity	Description	Also see	Human resource	Other resources	Cost needed (from OECS / GPE grant)	May 2021	Jun 2021	Jul 2021	Aug 2021	Sep 2021	Oct 2021	Nov 2021	Dec 2021	Jan 2022	Feb 2022
Component 1. Supporting teachers and instructors	Teachers	1.3.1	TPD - Co-facilitation and delivery	Teachers to co-facilitate TPD sessions, and to attend sessions regularly		Teachers and facilitators	N/A	N/A										

Component 2. Diagnostic tools and assessment					Months (funded)												Months (supported with existing resources)		
Component	Responsible	No.	Activity	Description	Also see	Human resource	Other resources	Cost needed (from OECS / GPE grant)	May 2021	Jun 2021	Jul 2021	Aug 2021	Sep 2021	Oct 2021	Nov 2021	Dec 2021	Jan 2022	Feb 2022	
* Ministry of Education / EDMU																			
Component 2. Diagnostic tools and assessment	Ministry of Education / EDMU	2.1.1.	Monitoring of diagnostic test data	Ensure that, from the earliest stages, diagnostic test data is sufficiently incorporated into monitoring frameworks. The EDMU needs to review their respective national education monitoring frameworks and decide on key indicators (e.g., student attendance, student performance, teacher qualifications and capabilities, etc).		EDMU-ARP team	The EDMU may need advice from an agency or consultant in review of their national plans.	TBD	█										
Component 2. Diagnostic tools and assessment	Ministry of Education / EDMU	2.1.2.	Record progress in diagnostic testing.	Record the total number of children in the school system, disaggregated by boys / girls, when they have been assessed, and whether they are participating in the programme or not. Record the results in the sheet provided ('Participation', also see 'Participation - Guidance').															
* Teachers																			
Component 2. Diagnostic tools and assessment	Teachers	2.2.1	Planning and administering diagnostic tests	Plan which tests will be used, when they will be used, how results will be graded / evaluated, and how results will be used to identify struggling students in particular. Plan frequency of test scheduling. Where necessary, update or adapt new diagnostic tests.		Teachers	The Caribbean battery tests can be used for diagnostic tests. If those are not available, sample diagnostic tests from other sources can be adapted: - Uwezo's National Learning Assessment (Kenya) - ASER Centre's English reading and Mathematics assessment tools (India)	TBD	█				█					█	
Component 2. Diagnostic tools and assessment	Teachers	2.2.2	Incorporate test results into lesson plans and pre- and reteaching activities	During TPD sessions and otherwise, teachers devise lesson activities and lesson plans, incorporating diagnostic analysis to address gaps and offer differentiation (e.g. through pre- and reteaching activities). Combine TPD session lessons on diagnostic tools with own insights from previous observations, and consider how to carry out these activities in both face-to-face and blended learning environments.	1, 2.2.4	Teachers / principals	Lesson plans, monitoring framework to record and track student performance, tests analysis	TBD		█	█	█		█	█	█			█
Component 2. Diagnostic tools and assessment	Teachers	2.2.3	Building diagnostic tests for SPED	SPED teachers and teachers who teach SPED students need support. Diagnostic tests must be developed or adapted which take account of the needs and learning styles of SPED students.	3	SPED teachers / classroom teachers / designated support staff where there is no SPED teacher	Printed copies of tests / soft copies in the event of lock down	N/A	█	█	█								
Component 2. Diagnostic tools and assessment	Teachers	2.2.4	Delivery of TPD on diagnostic tests	TPD sessions on diagnostic teaching sessions designed and delivered to teachers. This must include diagnostic tests for SPED students	1, 2.2.1, 3	Facilitators	Printed TPD manual / soft copies should be made available to teachers	N/A					█					█	

Results-based monitoring and evaluation framework for the ARP

Instructions: Fill in the red cells. Do not fill in the grey cells. Some tips are displayed in the sheet. See "Participation - Guidance" for a worked example.

Month	10th May 2021	17th May 2021	24th May 2021	31st May 2021	7th Jun 2021	mid Jun 2021	Jul 2021	Aug 2021	Sep 2021	Oct 2021	Nov 2021	Dec 2021	Jan 2022	Feb 2022			
Total boys in primary	[1]								[2]	[3]							
Total girls in primary																	
Boys of primary age not enrolled in school																	
Girls of primary age not enrolled in school																	
Total boys of primary school age	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total girls of primary school age	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total children	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Not yet assessed (boys)	[4]																
Not yet assessed (girls)																	
Assessed (boys)																	
Assessed (girls)																	
Need for recovery: Waiting to participate (boys)																	
Need for recovery: Waiting to participate (girls)																	
Need for recovery: Participating (boys)																	
Need for recovery: Participating (girls)																	
No need for recovery (boys)																	
No need for recovery (girls)																	
Percentages for assessment and participation																	
Percentage of boys assessed																	
Percentage of girls assessed																	
Percentage of all children assessed																	
Percentage of boys participating																	
Percentage of girls participating																	
Percentage of all children participating																	
Checks - the following numbers should be zero																	
Total boys = not yet assessed + assessed	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total girls = not yet assessed + assessed	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Assessed boys = waiting to participate + participating + no need	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Assessed girls = waiting to participate + participating + no need	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Results-based monitoring and evaluation framework for the ARP

Instructions: Some tips are displayed in the sheet. See "Participation - Guidance" for a worked example.

Month	10th May 2021	17th May 2021	24th May 2021	31st May 2021	7th Jun 2021	mid Jun 2021	Jul 2021	Aug 2021	Sep 2021	Oct 2021	Nov 2021	Dec 2021	Jan 2022	Feb 2022			
Total boys in primary	4,500 [5]	4,500	4,500	4,500					4,400 [6]	4,400 [7]							
Total girls in primary	5,000	5,000	5,000	5,000					5,100	5,100							
Boys of primary age not enrolled in school	0	0	0	0													
Girls of primary age not enrolled in school	0	0	0	0													
Total boys of primary school age	4,500	4,500	4,500	4,500	0	0	0		4,400	4,400	0	0	0	0			
Total girls of primary school age	5,000	5,000	5,000	5,000	0	0	0		5,100	5,100	0	0	0	0			
Total children	9,500	9,500	9,500	9,500	0	0	0		9,500	9,500	0	0	0	0			
Not yet assessed (boys)	4,500 [8]	500	0	0					300	0							
Not yet assessed (girls)	5,000	400	0	0					300	0							
Assessed (boys)	0	4,000	4,500	4,500					4,100	4,400							
Assessed (girls)	0	4,600	5,000	5,000					4,800	5,100							
Need for recovery: Waiting to participate (boys)	0	2,000	500	0					500	0							
Need for recovery: Waiting to participate (girls)	0	2,000	400	0					400	0							
Need for recovery: Participating (boys)	0	0	2,000	2,500					2,000	2,500							
Need for recovery: Participating (girls)	0	0	2,000	2,400					2,000	2,400							
No need for recovery (boys)	0	2,000	2,000	2,000					1,600	1,900							
No need for recovery (girls)	0	2,600	2,600	2,600					2,400	2,700							
Percentages for assessment and participation																	
Percentage of boys assessed	0%	89%	100%	100%					93%	100%							
Percentage of girls assessed	0%	92%	100%	100%					94%	100%							
Percentage of all children assessed	0%	91%	100%	100%					94%	100%							
Percentage of boys participating	0%	0%	80%	100%					71%	100%							
Percentage of girls participating	0%	0%	83%	100%					74%	100%							
Percentage of all children participating	0%	0%	82%	100%					73%	100%							
Checks - the following numbers should be zero																	
Total boys = not yet assessed + assessed	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		0	0	0	0	0	0			
Total girls = not yet assessed + assessed	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		0	0	0	0	0	0			
Assessed boys = waiting to participate + participating + no need	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		0	0	0	0	0	0			
Assessed girls = waiting to participate + participating + no need	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		0	0	0	0	0	0			

Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)								Months (funded)					Months (supported with existing resources)					
Component	Responsible	No.	Activity	Description	Also see	Human resource	Other resources	Cost needed (from OECS / GPE grant)	May 2021	Jun 2021	Jul 2021	Aug 2021	Sep 2021	Oct 2021	Nov 2021	Dec 2021	Jan 2022	Feb 2022
* Ministry of Education / EDMU																		
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	Ministry of Education / EDMU	3.1.1	Evaluate the current digital divide with regard to SPED	Carry out an audit of the digital divide in the respective member state focussing students with special educational needs.		EDMU-ARP team	N/A	Consultant										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	Ministry of Education / EDMU	3.1.2	Ensure robust M&E systems and identification processes	Put in place robust quality assurance monitoring and evaluation systems to ensure appropriate delivery. Ensure a national-level process for identifying SPED students is in place. This could involve implementing some digital tools.		EDMU-ARP team	N/A	Consultant if required										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	Ministry of Education / EDMU	3.1.3	Clearly define the roles of stakeholders	Review and provide role clarity for teachers and other professionals so that they understand their responsibilities for ensuring the learning continuity of SPED students.	1	EDMU-ARP team	N/A	N/A										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	Ministry of Education / EDMU	3.1.4	Close technology and resource gaps	Take action to close the household-level technology gaps, particularly for SPED students. Determine how students with SPED can be supported with assistive technologies and ensure that such technologies are made available. Distribution of tablets, books and resources to SPED students as needed	5	EDMU-ARP team	Relevant technology and printed material. Assistive technology for hearing impaired, visually impaired and other disabilities where necessary.	Cost for assistive devices.										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	Ministry of Education / EDMU	3.1.5	Provide resources to teachers and instructors	Provide resources and training for teachers to deliver distance education. Develop specific TPD sessions and resources for SPED teachers.	1, 2, 20	Facilitors / SPED coordinator	Printed or other material.	TBD										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	Ministry of Education / EDMU	3.1.6	Build partnerships with parents / caregivers	Build coalitions with parents or caregivers and non-government organisations to support continuity of learning for disadvantaged students.	5, 6, 20	MoE staff, parents, NGOs	Contact details of relevant personnel	N/A										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	Ministry of Education / EDMU	3.1.7	Work towards increased staffing	Develop plans to increase the number of school counsellors and educational psychologist. Determine appropriate long-term funds to support such staff.	3.1.9	Human resource manager / staff	Job description, budget	N/A										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	Ministry of Education / EDMU	3.1.8	Content sourcing for SPED	Sourcing and curation of content for SPED students	3.4.6	MoE Staff, one SPED coordinator	Inventory of selected SPED needs	TBD										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	Ministry of Education / EDMU	3.1.9	Recruit and train more SPED teachers and instructors	Where budget allows, give consideration to hiring of additional SPED instructors, teaching assistants and specialists. In addition, provide training for already existing SPED instructors.	3.1.7	Human resource manager / staff SPED trainers	N/A	XCD \$2000-\$4000 per month depending on experience										
* Ministry of Education / EDMU																		
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	Ministry of Health	3.2.1	Collaborate with MoE on diagnosis	Determine whether MoH staff can support diagnosing SPED students.	2	MoH staff, SPED teacher	N/A	N/A										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	Ministry of Health	3.2.2	Collaborate with MoE on strategy	Work collaboratively with MoE to define / refine the SPED referral strategy.		MoE staff, MoH staff, one SPED coordinator	N/A	N/A										

Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)									Months (funded)					Months (supported with existing resources)				
Component	Responsible	No.	Activity	Description	Also see	Human resource	Other resources	Cost needed (from OECS / GPE grant)	May 2021	Jun 2021	Jul 2021	Aug 2021	Sep 2021	Oct 2021	Nov 2021	Dec 2021	Jan 2022	Feb 2022
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	Ministry of Health	3.2.3	Contribute to designing of TPD	Support the design and delivery of SPED sessions (especially those linked with identifying disabilities).	2	MoH staff (counsellor), Facilitator, SPED coordinator	N/A	N/A										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	Ministry of Health	3.2.4	Awareness campaign rollout	Work collaboratively with parents and schools to sensitise them about disabilities and reduce stigma. The awareness campaign could utilise TV, radio and news papers. For example, radio clips could be produced and broadcast and 'advertisements' could be taken out in newspapers.	5, 6, 20	MoH staff, SPED coordinators, SPED teachers principals	Funding needed for production of content. Funding needed e.g. for taking out newspaper advertisements.	TBD										
* School administrators and principal																		
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	School administrators and principals	3.3.1	Engage with SPED identification processes	Follow up on referrals of cases of students with suspected SPED needs, and facilitate connection with relevant specialists as needed.		SPED coordinators, SPED teachers, classroom teachers	N/A	N/A										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	School administrators and principals	3.3.2	Partnerships with SPED specialists and organisations	Establish strategic partnerships with specialist SPED schools to enable resource sharing, as well as with advocacy and support organisations such as Disabled Peoples' International North America and the Caribbean.		SPED coordinators, SPED teachers, classroom teachers	List with contact details of strategic partners	N/A										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	School administrators and principals	3.3.3	Keep records of SPED students	Maintain a record of students with SPED needs progress through the education system, allowing teachers to hand over and ensure a proper level of support.		SPED coordinators, SPED teachers, classroom teachers	Record of student progress	N/A										
* Teachers																		
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	SPED / classroom teachers	3.4.1	SPED student evaluation / planning	Develop co planning and co teaching schedules with support staff Establish time to plan and evaluate teaching, student performance and next steps Plan monitoring and evaluation frameworks for ongoing evaluation and monitoring Evaluate the effectiveness of peer tutoring, parental engagement, assessment ect. Decide on the framework for evaluating the effectiveness of monitoring and evaluation activities in the past 2 months Devise a plan for next steps		SPED coordinators, SPED teachers,	Schedules and list of support staff	N/A										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	SPED / classroom teachers	3.4.2	Engaging parents of SPED students	Devise plan to engage all parents of SPED students and develop novel means to involve those who are reluctant to participate. Devise a training plan for parents. One that will equip them with necessary skills to support their children at home. In cases where parents are unable to support their children, plan for an alternative form of support		SPED coordinators, SPED teachers, classroom teachers, parents	Printed and soft copies of plans	XCD \$5 per copy										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	SPED / classroom teachers	3.4.3	Supporting SPED students	Consider how peer relationships, tutoring and mentoring for SPED students can supplement the activity of specialist teachers.		SPED / classroom teachers	N/A	N/A										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	SPED / classroom teachers	3.4.4	Participate in TPD sessions	Some of the TPD sessions focus on support for SPED students. In particular, those sessions would focus on differentiation (planning lessons and small group activities) the various learning needs of SPED students.		SPED / classroom teachers	N/A	N/A										

Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)									Months (funded)					Months (supported with existing resources)				
Component	Responsible	No.	Activity	Description	Also see	Human resource	Other resources	Cost needed (from OECS / GPE grant)	May 2021	Jun 2021	Jul 2021	Aug 2021	Sep 2021	Oct 2021	Nov 2021	Dec 2021	Jan 2022	Feb 2022
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	SPED / classroom teachers	3.4.5	Keep records, use support plans and referrals	Contribute to record-keeping and implement support plans as necessary. Understand and use referral mechanisms where necessary.		SPED / classroom teachers School administrators	N/A	N/A										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	SPED / classroom teachers	3.4.6	Source for content online	Source for open-source content for SPED students and integrate into lessons plans.	3.1.8	SPED / classroom teachers	Determine what content should be procured	Funding needed for procuring specialist resources										
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	SPED / classroom teachers	3.4.7	Administer diagnostic tests and deliver feedback	Administer diagnostic tests to assess children's learning progress. Provide regular feedback to students.		SPED / classroom teachers	N/A	N/A										

Component 4. Resource library: Open Educational Resources								Months (funded)					Months (supported with existing resources)					
Component	Responsible	No.	Activity	Description	Also see	Human resource	Other resources	Cost needed (from OECS / GPE grant)	May 2021	Jun 2021	Jul 2021	Aug 2021	Sep 2021	Oct 2021	Nov 2021	Dec 2021	Jan 2022	Feb 2022
* Ministry of Education/EDMU																		
Component 4. Resource library: Open Educational Resources	Ministry of Education / EDMU	4.1.1	Content inventory	Carry out a content inventory of all the relevant content existing and identify content gaps.		MoE staff / ARP Team	N/A	N/A										
Component 4. Resource library: Open Educational Resources	Ministry of Education / EDMU	4.1.2	Content sourcing	Establishing a database of all readily available content (OER where possible).		MoE staff	N/A	N/A										
Component 4. Resource library: Open Educational Resources	Ministry of Education / EDMU	4.1.3	Review content	Review all the content collected on the basis of cultural relevance, quality and curriculum alignment.		MoE staff / ARP Team	N/A	N/A										
Component 4. Resource library: Open Educational Resources	Ministry of Education / EDMU	4.1.4	Content curation and alignment	Based on the review exercise, align content to the different subjects in the curriculum and upload it to a shared platform (such as the OECS ELP platform or Kolibri) which teachers and learners can access. Content should contain materials adapted for SPED students, as well as materials on pair tutoring, talk, and play.	1, 3	MoE staff	N/A	N/A										
Component 4. Resource library: Open Educational Resources	Ministry of Education / EDMU	4.1.5	Material development	For subjects where suitable content is not available online, instructional designers can be hired—or recruited as volunteers—to create relevant content. Given its time- and resource-intensive nature, this process should only be undertaken where appropriate content is not already available.		MoE staff, teachers, principals, community members	N/A	Contracted teachers										
* School administrators and principals																		
Component 4. Resource library: Open Educational Resources	School administrators and principals	4.2.1	Collate required inventory of resources	Compile a required inventory of all resources required by teachers, and review existing resources available to them	4.1.1, 4.1.2, 4.1.3	Principal, teacher	N/A	N/A										
Component 4. Resource library: Open Educational Resources	School administrators and principals	4.2.2	Resource allocation and pooling	Develop resource budget and plan allocation of resources. Consider whether pooling / sharing resources with other schools may be an effective solution.		Principal, teacher	N/A	N/A										
Component 4. Resource library: Open Educational Resources	School administrators and principals	4.2.3	Test OERs and ensure teacher competency	Before launching OERs, ensure that teachers are all competent in their use, and support them where this competency needs developing.		Principal, assistant principal	N/A	N/A										
* Teachers																		
Component 4. Resource library: Open Educational Resources	Teachers	4.3.1	Resource inventory and allocation	Compile a list of resources that you will need (including both online and offline resources)	4.1.1, 4.1.2, 4.1.3	Principal, assistant principal	Resource list	N/A										
Component 4. Resource library: Open Educational Resources	Teachers	4.3.2	Resource storage and access management	Teachers need to support each other in use of resources. Ensure that all teachers in the school have access to the content repository.	4.2.2	Teacher	N/A	N/A										
Component 4. Resource library: Open Educational Resources	Teachers	4.3.3	Ensure safeguarding of students and student information	Where student access online learning environments, ensure that students are using safe logins. Make children aware of some the risks of accessing content online.	3	Teacher	N/A	N/A										

Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents and caregivers									Months (funded)					Months (supported with existing resources)				
Component	Responsible	No.	Activity	Description	Also see	Human resource	Other resources	Cost needed (from OECS / GPE grant)	May 2021	Jun 2021	Jul 2021	Aug 2021	Sep 2021	Oct 2021	Nov 2021	Dec 2021	Jan 2022	Feb 2022
Ministry of Education / EDMU																		
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	Ministry of Education / EDMU	5.1.1	Conduct parental needs assessment	Work in collaboration with schools to collect information on the needs of parents and caregivers. Design a questionnaire that schools may use to collect this information.		MoE staff, principal, parents and caregivers, teachers	N/A	Consultant	█	█								
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	Ministry of Education / EDMU	5.1.2	Review existing content created for parents	Review some of the content and materials made available to parents since the start of the pandemic and get feedback on whether it was useful.		MoE staff, principal	N/A	Consultant	█									
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	Ministry of Education / EDMU	5.1.3	Update exiting content for parents and develop new content as needed	Based on the findings in the first two stages, proceed to produce or repurpose content geared towards helping parents engage more actively in their children's education. Producing short and informative radio content suggested. Parents must be involved in the design of these tools. Content should include pair mentoring with siblings / friends and the importance of talking and play activities.		MoE Staff, possible collaboration with local producers for radio content, parents, possible input from students	Drafts for radio content / storyboards	Production costs		█								
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	Ministry of Education / EDMU	5.1.4	Roll out content	Make all content produced available to parents.		MoE / principals, PTA	Printed material	TBD			█							
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	Ministry of Education / EDMU	5.1.5	Radio campaign	Create brief instructional radio scripts informing parents on best practice to support their child / children at home. Ideally, information should be brief and aired during prime time on a daily basis during a coordinated, intense campaign. Information should also be practical and relatable to the circumstances of a variety of parents.		MoE, actors & producers	Completed radio scripts / storyboards	Production costs				█						
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	Ministry of Education / EDMU	5.1.6	Redefine counsellor roles	Revisit guideline for the role of counsellors during the pandemic.		MoE staff, SPED coordinator input may be vital	N/A	N/A				█						
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	Ministry of Education / EDMU	5.1.7	Develop plan for increasing the number of counsellors	Consider finance and process for hiring new counsellors.		MoE / ARP Team, human resource management	Office, equipment etc. required by new staff	Long-term investment should be considered						█	█	█	█	█
School administrators and principals																		
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	School administrators and principals	5.2.1	Support parental needs assessment	Ensure the dissemination of the questionnaire produced by the MoE to assess the needs of parents and caregivers.	5.1.1	Principal, teachers	Printed questionnaires	TBD	█									
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	School administrators and principals	5.2.2	Make information available to the designated authorities	Present this information to the designated authorities in the prescribed format.	5.1.4, 5.1.5	Principal, teachers	Printed materials, such as posters for schools, community centres, etc.	TBD			█							
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	School administrators and principals	5.2.3	Inform parents about the availability of new content	Once the content is ready to be disseminated, inform parents and caregivers about its availability and make it available to them.	5.1.5	Principal, teachers	N/A	N/A				█						
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	School administrators and principals	5.2.4	Strengthen links with PTA	Coordinate with local and national PTAs to ensure that parents understand their roles and perform them effectively.	7	Principal, assistant principal, point persons from PTA	List of both local and national PTA	TBD				█	█	█	█	█	█	█
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	School administrators and principals	5.2.5	Developing engagement protocols for parents	Define a protocol for parental support, stating exactly what is expected of them in supporting blended learning. Develop a list of alternative ways to engage them (materials, training etc.), and a schedule for engagement. Pay attention to parents' psychosocial needs.		Parents, assistant principal	Printed material, training schedule	TBD		█								
Teachers																		

Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents and caregivers									Months (funded)					Months (supported with existing resources)				
Component	Responsible	No.	Activity	Description	Also see	Human resource	Other resources	Cost needed (from OECS / GPE grant)	May 2021	Jun 2021	Jul 2021	Aug 2021	Sep 2021	Oct 2021	Nov 2021	Dec 2021	Jan 2022	Feb 2022
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	Teachers	5.3.1	Disseminate and collect questionnaires	Send questionnaires to students' parents and ensure that they complete them to identify parents particularly in need of support.		Teachers, parents	Printed questionnaires, soft copies can also be emailed	TBD										
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	Teachers	5.3.2	Submit questionnaire responses	Submit responses to the school administrator in the required format.		Teachers, principals	Completed questionnaires	N/A										
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	Teachers	5.3.3	Support dissemination of resources to parents	Support the dissemination of ARP resources to parents once available.	5.2.2, 5.2.3	Teachers	Printed and soft copies of material	TBD										
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	Teachers	5.3.4	Identify, support, and refer	Identify students and families in need of intervention, engaging them directly, or referring to counsellors and / or SPED specialists where possible	5.1.1, 5.2.1, 5.1.6, 5.1.7, 6	Classroom teachers, SPED teachers	List of students and families in need of support	TBD										

Component 6. Community engagement									Months (funded)					Months (supported with existing resources)				
Component	Responsible	No.	Activity	Description	Also see	Human resource	Other resources	Cost needed (from OECS / GPE grant)	May 2021	Jun 2021	Jul 2021	Aug 2021	Sep 2021	Oct 2021	Nov 2021	Dec 2021	Jan 2022	Feb 2022
* Ministry of Education / EDMU																		
Component 6. Community engagement	Ministry of Education / EDMU	6.1.1	Identify organisations and individuals	Identify community based-organisations and individuals who offer catch up lessons or remedial education to children. These may include faith-based groups, youth groups etc. The evaluation could be supported by local consultants who have access to community organisations. The evaluation could potentially be led by a community organisation.		MoE staff / ARP Team, principals	Existing lists of community organisations, the locations in which the operate (across different districts / territories), contact details (where available).	Consultant										
Component 6. Community engagement	Ministry of Education / EDMU	6.1.2	Define shared goals / objectives	Explain the goals of the ARP to community figures and identify potential areas for collaboration.		MoE staff and community organisations; consider input from principals	N/A	N/A										
Component 6. Community engagement	Ministry of Education / EDMU	6.1.3	Establish a role for appropriate individuals and organisations	Based on the findings in the first two steps, establish clearly-defined roles and goals of the community organisations within the ARP context.		MoE staff and community organisations; principals	N/A	N/A										
* School administrators and principals																		
Component 6. Community engagement	School administrators and principals	6.2.1	Involve teachers and staff	Involve the teachers and auxiliary staff in understanding the importance of school and community partnerships.		Principals, support staff, teachers	N/A	N/A										
Component 6. Community engagement	School administrators and principals	6.2.2	Set up a community engagement team	Set up a community engagement team of about 2-4 teachers responsible for identifying and approaching community group leaders and relevant organisations / individuals.		Principals, support staff, teachers	List of community engagement team	N/A										
Component 6. Community engagement	School administrators and principals	6.2.3	Approach community group leaders	Organise meetings with community leaders and relevant organisations / individuals to explain the ARP's scope and content. Emphasise the importance of the role they have to play. Discuss potential ways they can complement the programme. Formalise and record mutual commitments.		Principals, support staff, teachers	List of community leaders	N/A										
Component 6. Community engagement	School administrators and principals	6.2.4	Engage partners	Work collaboratively with identified leaders, organisations, and individuals to define the scope of their role in the ARP.		Principals, support staff, teachers	Funding for transport and events is needed.	TBD										
Component 6. Community engagement	School administrators and principals	6.2.5	Promote counselling and referrals as needed	Explain the counsellor's role to staff, students, and parents.	1, 5	Principals, support staff, teachers	In some case, list of resources to use to promote counselling	N/A										
Component 6. Community engagement	School administrators and principals	6.2.6	Evaluate training needs	Evaluate the training needs of participating groups.		Principals, support staff, teachers	Framework for evaluating training needs	N/A										
Component 6. Community engagement	School administrators and principals	6.2.7	Implement training and processes	Establish and implement a training schedule, protocols, and monitoring practices.		Principal, assistant principal, facilitator	printed material, soft copies of materials,	TBD										
* Teachers																		
Component 6. Community engagement	Teachers	6.3.1	Join / support community engagement team	Join the community engagement working group or provide support by providing information contacts the school can approach.		Support staff, teachers, community team	Funding for transport and events is needed.	TBD										

Component 7. Cross-sectoral partnerships								Months (funded)					Months (supported with existing resources)					
Component	Responsible	No.	Activity	Description	Also see	Human resource	Other resources	Cost needed (from OECS / GPE grant)	May 2021	Jun 2021	Jul 2021	Aug 2021	Sep 2021	Oct 2021	Nov 2021	Dec 2021	Jan 2022	Feb 2022
* Ministry of Education / EDMU																		
Component 7. Partnerships	Ministry of Education / EDMU / EDMU	7.1.1	Desk-based research	Undertake desk-based review of all the current actors in the field and create or update a database with relevant information about their operations. The evaluation could be supported by local consultants to assess partnerships.	4, 5, 20	MoE staff / ARP Team Local consultant	Database / monitoring framework	Cost for local consultant										
Component 7. Partnerships	Ministry of Education / EDMU / EDMU	7.1.2	Partnership modelling	Based on the information gathered, review partnership models as they are best suited for (primary and secondary) learners. Some partnership models to be explored include brokering, and providing support, and establishing networks.	7.1.1	MoE staff, various partners	Database / monitoring framework	N/A										
Component 7. Partnerships	Ministry of Education / EDMU / EDMU	7.1.3	Partnership evaluation	Carry out an audit of all existing partnerships to determine the state of those existing partnerships.		MoE staff, principal input may be vital	List of current partners / data base with partner information	N/A										
Component 7. Partnerships	Ministry of Education / EDMU / EDMU	7.1.4	Establish new partnerships	Establish new partnerships with relevant actors and incorporate them into monitoring frameworks as necessary. Partnerships need to be built with organisations that can support students with SPED needs.	4	MoE staff, principal input	Database / monitoring framework	N/A										
Component 7. Partnerships	Ministry of Education / EDMU / EDMU	7.1.6	Record keeping	Maintain and update records of partnerships, as well as renewed searches to identify new potential partners		MoE staff, principals	Database / monitoring framework	N/A										
* School administrators and principals																		
Component 7. Partnerships	School Administrators and Principals	7.2.1	Inform teachers about partnerships	Inform teachers, parents and auxiliary staff of the importance of creating partnerships for the ARP.	1, 5	Principal / assistant principal, support staff, teachers, parents	Presentation	N/A										
Component 7. Partnerships	School administrators and principals	7.2.2	Review existing partnerships	Carry out audits on all existing partnerships to determine the state and viability of existing partnerships. Potential indicators include power balance, shared values, common goals and the overall impact.		Principal / assistant principal	Database / monitoring framework	N/A										
Component 7. Partnerships	School administrators and principals	7.2.3	Set up partnerships working group	Set up a partnership task force of teachers who will identify local organisations or institutions who could be potential partners (this could also include resourceful parents).	1	Principal / assistant principal, support staff, teachers, parents	Travel and meetings	TBD										
Component 7. Partnerships	School administrators and principals	7.2.4	Identify potential partners	Identify potential partners and collaborators (in this case, nearby schools, community and faith-based organisations, service providers) who may help the ARP. Feed this information back to relevant stakeholders, including the district education management officer, if necessary.	6	Principals, teachers, parents, support staff	Database or list with relevant partners / monitoring framework. Should contain current, new and potential partners	N/A										
Component 7. Partnerships	School administrators and principals	7.2.5	Check for aligned goals and values	Approach potential partners to identify common goals, shared interests, and values.	6	Principal, potential partners	Printed online of school goals, interests, values and so on	N/A										
Component 7. Partnerships	School administrators and principals	7.2.6	Establish new partnerships	Establish new partnerships with relevant actors and incorporate them into monitoring frameworks as necessary.	6	Principal, potential partners	Monitoring framework	N/A										
Component 7. Partnerships	School administrators and principals	7.2.7	Determining the nature of partnerships	Once partners are selected and the nature of partnerships are established, set up training schedule for those who will provide mentorship and or training. Identify what will be provided and when, considering storage and maintenance where relevant.	6	Principal, potential partners	Schedules	N/A										
* Teachers																		
Component 7. Partnerships	Teachers	7.3.1	Participate in ARP staff meetings	Participating in ARP-related staff meetings will enable teachers to understand the nature and importance of partnerships for ARP success and longevity.	1	Principals, teachers, potential partners	N/A	N/A										
Component 7. Partnerships	Teachers	7.3.2	Join or support ARP partnerships taskforce	Teachers can either join their school's (or district's) partnership task force or provide support in identifying potential partners for community organisations.	1	Principals, teachers, potential partners	N/A	N/A										

Results-based monitoring and evaluation framework for the ARP							
Component	Responsible	Activities	Outputs	Performance indicators	Means of verification	Outcome	Assumptions
Component 1. Supporting teachers and instructors	Ministry of Education / EDMU School administrators and principals Teachers	1.1.1. Planning psychosocial and social support for teaching staff and instructors 1.1.2. Establish support network for teachers 1.1.3. TPD - Session plans 1.1.4. Implementing psychosocial / social support for teaching staff and instructors 1.2.1. TPD - Facilitator selection 1.2.2. TPD - Planning 1.2.3. TPD - Material production and distribution 1.2.4. TPD - Evaluation 1.3.1. TPD - Co-facilitation and delivery	Delivery TPD sessions for academic recovery with - high-quality materials, - weekly participation from teachers. Establishment of a support network for teachers.	Number of sessions organised Number of participants in TPD sessions	Attendance records of participants in the TPD sessions; M&E forms Facilitator's report on sessions	Teachers and instructors receive adequate training and support needed to deliver and monitor the ARP	Teachers are available to attend and participate in PD sessions Teachers remain motivated throughout Resources required to deliver the sessions are available
Component 2. Diagnostic tools and assessment	Ministry of Education / EDMU Teachers	2.1.1.. Monitoring of diagnostic test data 2.1.2.. Record progress in diagnostic testing. 2.2.1. Planning and administering diagnostic tests 2.2.2. Incorporate test results into lesson plans and pre- and reteaching activities 2.2.3. Building diagnostic tests for SPED 2.2.4. Delivery of TPD on diagnostic tests	Monitoring of diagnostic test results at schools, district and national levels Diagnostic tests available to all teachers TPD sessions manuals for facilitators and teachers	Diagnostic tests available (for learning loss, for SPED) Number of assessments administered to students Test administration records and results Decisions made on basis of test outcomes	List of students who need help document / database Individual support measures reported by teachers Lesson plans informed by diagnostic data	Diagnostic tools are used effectively by teachers to assess children and identify students who need help	Students are available to take diagnostic tests Teachers have the time to administer (and grade) the diagnostic tests
Component 3. Special education and disability (SPED)	Ministry of Education / EDMU Ministry of Health School administrators and principals SPED / classroom teachers	3.1.1. Evaluate the current digital divide with regard to SPED 3.1.2. Ensure robust M&E systems and identification processes 3.1.3. Clearly define the roles of stakeholders 3.1.4. Close technology and resource gaps 3.1.5. Provide resources to teachers and instructors 3.1.6. Build partnerships with parents / caregivers 3.1.7. Work towards increased staffing 3.1.8. Content sourcing for SPED 3.1.9. Recruit and train more SPED teachers and instructors 3.2.1. Collaborate with MoE on diagnosis 3.2.2. Collaborate with MoE on strategy 3.2.3. Contribute to designing of TPD 3.2.4. Awareness campaign rollout 3.3.1. Engage with SPED identification processes 3.3.2. Partnerships with SPED specialists and organisations 3.3.3. Keep records of SPED students 3.4.1. SPED student evaluation / planning 3.4.2. Engaging parents of SPED students 3.4.3. Supporting SPED students 3.4.4. Participate in TPD sessions 3.4.5. Keep records, use support plans and referrals 3.4.6. Source for content online 3.4.7. Administer diagnostic tests and deliver feedback	TPD sessions and resources for SPED (and non-SPED) teachers Content repository for SPED students SPED students provided with materials / devices Awareness campaign rolled out Referral system strengthened	Number of newly recruited SPED staff Number of books / tablets and resources delivered SPED students Availability of SPED content repository Attendance records for SPED TPD sessions	Distribution records of resources and devices to SPED children Facilitator report on SPED TPD Sessions Availability of SPED content repository Records of SPED student referrals and action plans	Children with special education needs have access to resources for ARP, and teachers are able to understand and respond to the needs of SPED students	Ministries have allocated funding to provide resources to SPED children There are trained individuals for SPED available for employment There is enough open source content for SPED children online
Component 4. Resource library: Open Educational Resources	Ministry of Education / EDMU School administrators and principals Teachers	4.1.1. Content inventory 4.1.2. Content sourcing 4.1.3. Review content 4.1.4. Content curation and alignment 4.1.5. Material development 4.2.1. Collate required inventory of resources 4.2.2. Resource allocation and pooling 4.2.3. Test OERs and ensure teacher competency 4.3.1. Resource inventory and allocation 4.3.2. Resource storage and access management 4.3.3. Ensure safeguarding of students and student information	Mechanisms for sharing content among territories and among schools. An online content repository aligned with relevant national curricula is established (or an existing repository is used by all partners).	Number of teachers engaging with open resource platforms Number of teachers engaging with aligned curriculum	OECS resource library available online	The OECS has a fully developed resource library. Teachers are accessing and adapting materials for use in school work, between schools where relevant.	Teachers are willing to engage with the platform Schools are confidently engaging with aligned curriculum Aligned curriculum is responsive to current academic / training needs
Component 5. Engaging and supporting parents	Ministry of Education / EDMU School administrators and principals Teachers	5.1.1. Conduct parental needs assessment 5.1.2. Review existing content created for parents 5.1.3. Update exiting content for parents and develop new content as needed 5.1.4. Roll out content 5.1.5. Radio campaign 5.1.6. Redefine counsellor roles 5.1.7. Develop plan for increasing the number of counsellors 5.2.1. Support parental needs assessment 5.2.2. Make information available to the designated authorities 5.2.3. Inform parents about the availability of new content 5.2.4. Strengthen links with PTA 5.2.5. Developing engagement protocols for parents 5.3.1. Disseminate and collect questionnaires 5.3.2. Submit questionnaire responses 5.3.3. Support dissemination of resources to parents 5.3.4. Identify, support, and refer	Parents' resource toolkit (videos, podcasts, and print resources) Radio campaign at national level Parental engagement protocols and content for parents	Number of messages received by teachers from parents Number of 'new' parents attending PTA meetings	Availability of parents ARP resource PTA meeting report(s) detailing attendance	Parents are actively engaged in their children's education	Parents are confident in how to effectively support their children at home Parents are willing to collaborate with teachers Parents support interventions from community groups

Results-based monitoring and evaluation framework for the ARP							
Component	Responsible	Activities	Outputs	Performance indicators	Means of verification	Outcome	Assumptions
Component 6. Community engagement	Ministry of Education / EDMU School administrators and principals Teachers	6.1.1. Identify organisations and individuals 6.1.2. Define shared goals / objectives 6.1.3. Establish a role for appropriate individuals and organisations 6.2.1. Involve teachers and staff 6.2.2. Set up a community engagement team 6.2.3. Approach community group leaders 6.2.4. Engage partners 6.2.5. Promote counselling and referrals as needed 6.2.6. Evaluate training needs 6.2.7. Implement training and processes 6.3.1. Join / support community engagement team	List of identified organisations and individuals Document reporting shared goals / objectives Community engagement team established Document describing training needs and approach to training	Number of organisations identified Community engagement is establishing relationships with community organisations	List of identified organisations and individuals Document reporting shared goals / objectives Document describing training needs and approach to training	Greater collaboration with the community reduces pressure on teachers and provides better opportunities for weaker students to learn	Community organisations are willing to contribute
Component 7. Partnerships	Ministry of Education / EDMU / EDMU School Administrators and Principals School administrators and principals Teachers	7.1.1. Desk-based research 7.1.2. Partnership modelling 7.1.3. Partnership evaluation 7.1.4. Establish new partnerships 7.1.6. Record keeping 7.2.1. Inform teachers about partnerships 7.2.2. Review existing partnerships 7.2.3. Set up partnerships working group 7.2.4. Identify potential partners 7.2.5. Check for aligned goals and values 7.2.6. Establish new partnerships 7.2.7. Determining the nature of partnerships 7.3.1. Participate in ARP staff meetings 7.3.2. Join or support ARP partnerships taskforce	Partnerships mapping document List of existing partners and new potential partners (including industry and commerce).	Number of meetings organised with partners New partnership deals established.	Submitted and approved partnerships mapping report Number of new partnership contracts or renewals	Sustainable strategic cross-sectoral partnerships have been established to support the planning, monitoring and delivery of the ARP	Stakeholders are willing to work together Stakeholders share common values and goals

[1] Start by entering the number of boys in primary, this will fill all the top row

[2] With the new school year, the number may change slightly.

[3] With the new school year, the number may change slightly.

[4] In month 1 (May) you should enter all boys / girls as not assessed. By assessed we mean assessed under the ARP, not due to prior assessments.

[5] Start by entering the number of boys in primary, this will fill all the top row

[6] With the new school year, the number may change slightly.

[7] With the new school year, the number may change slightly.

[8] In month 1 (May) you should enter all boys / girls as not assessed. By assessed we mean assessed under the ARP, not due to prior assessments.